

ENZYMES FROM ACTINOMYCETES: A LOOK AT THEIR CATALYTIC ROLES AND BIOTECHNOLOGICAL USES IN INDUSTRY

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Abstract. *Actinomycetes are Gram-positive, filamentous bacteria that are abundant in soil, plant tissues, and marine habitats. They are classified as phylum Actinobacteria. They are crucial to ecosystem nutrient recycling because of the roles they play in breaking down complex organic compounds. Many different industries rely on the valuable extracellular enzymes produced by actinomycetes. These enzymes like cellulases, proteases, amylases, lipases, xylanases, chitinases, cutinases, and pectinases break down organic materials and have many different uses, including in food processing, pharmaceuticals, textiles, detergents, pulp and paper, agriculture, biorefineries. The secretion of various hydrolytic and protease enzymes is a characteristic of Streptomyces. Acute lymphoblastic leukaemia is another common cancer treated using microbial L-asparaginase, which is made by a number of actinomycetes. There is promising evidence that actinomycetes found in harsh conditions can produce new enzymes that have important industrial uses.*

Keywords: *actinomycetes, Enzymes, Cellulase, Protease, Amylase.*

Introduction

Actinomycetes are Gram-positive bacteria that are filamentous and have a complicated life cycle. They are classified in the phylum Actinobacteria, which is one of the biggest taxonomic groupings among the 18 primary lineages recognized under the Domain Bacteria [16]. Soil is home to many different types of actinobacteria, and these microbes are crucial in the recycling of resistant biomaterials, such as the complex combinations of polymers found in the decaying matter of plants, animals, and fungi. Soil microbes play an essential role in decomposing organic matter and creating humus by reusing nutrients from insoluble polymers like chitin, keratin, and lignocelluloses [3;6;14]. In the process, they release volatile compounds like geosmin, which is said to be responsible for the "wet earth odour" [18] and they display a wide range of physiological and metabolic traits, such as creating extracellular enzymes [6;12].

Enzyme production from Actinomycetes

In order to digest food outside of cells, actinomycetes release amylases. In biotechnological applications like the food industry, fermentation, and textile to paper industries, α amylase starch degrading amylolytic enzymes play a crucial role [9]. Hydrolytic enzymes known as cellulases

break down the glucosidic linkages found in cellulose and other cello-digosaccharide derivatives [4]. In 2002, Kulkarni and Gadre found that certain actinomycetes, bacteria, and fungi produce lipase [5]. According to Schmidt et al. (1998), lipases find widespread use in many different industries, including those dealing with food, oleochemistry, diagnostics, and prescription drugs [11]. The ability of actinomycetes to manufacture and secrete a variety of extracellular hydrolytic enzymes makes them extremely important [10;15]. It has been observed that certain actinomycetes, such as Streptomyces, release many proteases into the culture media [13]. It has been found that actinomycetes are a great source of L-asparaginase. The ability to manufacture the L-asparaginase enzyme has been found in several actinomycetes, including those commonly found in soil, such as Streptomyces griseus, *S. karnatakensis*, *S. albidoflavus*, and *Nocardia* sp. [1;7;8]. Acute lymphoblastic leukaemia is one of the human cancers that has responded well to the use of microbial L-asparaginase as a treatment [2;17]. Additionally, actinomycetes generate the enzymes catalase, chitinase, and urease as mentioned in Fig.1.

Fig.1: Utilization of actinomycete-derived enzymes

Conclusions

Enzymes derived from microbes are in high demand in many industrial applications, according to recent research on their significance and practical use. Due to their ability to manufacture and secrete a wide range of environmentally friendly extracellular hydrolytic enzymes, actinomycetes are of paramount relevance. There are numerous industrial uses for the key biocatalysts produced by actinomycetes, which are extracellular enzymes. Actinomycetes are crucial to the production of industrial enzymes, which means they have the potential to solve numerous pressing issues in many different sectors, including the textile, biorefinery, food, pulp and paper, detergent, pharmaceutical, and agricultural industries.

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